

CLINICAL AND NEUROIMAGING ASSESSMENT OF THE DYNAMICS OF INTELLECTUAL AND MNESTIC FUNCTIONING IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS WITH MIGRAINE

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Abstract. *Migraine is one of the many pathologies of the nervous system, which, according to statistical data, is observed in 7.7% of children and adolescents in the general population. Migraine can manifest even before the age of three. As the child grows older, the prevalence of migraine increases, reaching 15% by adolescence. This pathology significantly reduces a child’s daily functional activity and academic performance. Diagnosing migraine in children poses certain challenges, and unfortunately, children with migraine are often misdiagnosed and prescribed inadequate treatment. Therefore, the search for, study, and implementation of the most effective methods for diagnosing and treating this pathology in children and adolescents is extremely important today.*

Keywords: *cephalalgia, migraine, children, adolescents, diagnosis.*

Introduction. At present, the term “migraine” is understood as a set of genetically induced pathological conditions, the fundamental characteristic features of which include pulsating, remitting headaches, usually localized on one side and lasting from 1–2 hours to several days. Moreover, in younger age groups, this pathology is more frequently detected in boys, whereas in adolescents it is more common in girls [1]. In some cases, the cephalic syndrome in migraine may be preceded by completely reversible ophthalmic, auditory, or sensory disturbances – so-called “aura” [2].

Migraine is considered one of the most common and simultaneously unfavorable forms of primary headache, which can drastically limit the activity of children and adolescents in both social and educational spheres and has a significantly negative impact on their overall quality of life. According to recently published data, migraine accounts for approximately 5.5–9.2% of all headaches [3]. Typically, the incidence of migraine increases throughout childhood: at the age of 3–7 years, it affects 1–3% of children; from 7 to 11 years, 4–11%; and in the 13 to 18-year range, it affects 8–28% of adolescents. Among adolescent boys, migraine is reported in 1.5% of cases, whereas among girls of the same age group it is reported in 7.2% of cases, giving a ratio of 1:4. In 20% of children, migraine develops before the age of five. The average age of disease onset is about seven years in boys and eleven years in girls.

In 70% of migraine headache cases, the condition is considered familial. Previous studies have clearly shown that in individuals whose first-degree relatives suffer from migraine, the risk of developing migraine attacks is 1.9 times higher than in the general population [4,5].

To classify various types of migraine, the International Classification of Headache Disorders, 3rd edition (ICHD-III, 2018) is currently used. According to this classification, in children and adolescents, the disease is subdivided into migraine without aura (MwA), migraine with aura (MA), chronic migraine, migraine complications, probable migraine, and episodic syndromes associated with migraine.

Classification of Migraine According to ICHD-III (2018):

1. Migraine
2. Migraine without aura (MwA)
3. Migraine with aura (MA), including:
 - Migraine with typical aura
 - Typical aura with headache
 - Typical aura without headache
 - Migraine with brainstem aura
 - Hemiplegic migraine
 - Familial hemiplegic migraine (three types)
 - Sporadic hemiplegic migraine
4. Retinal migraine
5. Chronic migraine
6. Migraine complications:
 - Status migrainosus
 - Persistent aura without infarction
 - Migrainous infarction
7. Episodic syndromes that may be associated with migraine:
 - Recurrent gastrointestinal disturbances
 - Cyclic vomiting syndrome
8. Abdominal migraine
9. Benign paroxysmal vertigo
10. Benign paroxysmal torticollis (wry neck) [6].

A considerable number of publications have been devoted to studying the etiopathogenetic processes of migraine. However, many unresolved questions remain. For example, the causal factors contributing to one of migraine's most critical components—pain—are still not fully understood, even though this pain is a key factor in disrupting the patient's quality of life.

Migraine-related pain manifests through cerebral blood vessels, their innervation by the trigeminal nerve system, and its reflexive associations with cranial vessels. In most cases, patients experience pain in the innervation zone of the first branch of the nervus trigeminus and/or the C2 cervical segment.

According to existing literature, it is assumed that migraine pain may result from the spread of cortical spreading depression (CSD) to the meningeal fibers of the trigeminal nerve, potentially triggering the release of vasoactive substances such as neurokinin A, substance P, and calcitonin gene-related peptide (CGRP) [7].

In addition to this, several theories attempt to explain the origin of migraine attacks:

Vascular Theory

According to this theory, a migraine attack consists of two phases. The prodromal phase is marked by vascular spasm, leading to cerebral ischemia and transient neurological symptoms. The second phase is characterized by compensatory vasodilation of intracranial and extra cranial

vessels. In recent decades, however, interest in the vascular theory has diminished. Studies have shown that the characteristic pulsating pain in migraine is more closely related to neuronal mechanisms and not to pathological activation of perivascular sensory fibers [8].

Metabolic Theory

This theory is among the most frequently cited explanations for migraine onset. Recent studies clearly demonstrate that certain types of migraine are associated with mitochondrial dysfunction [9]. Such dysfunction leads to increased calcium influx into cells, excessive secretion of free radicals, and disruption of oxidative phosphorylation. This combination causes an energy imbalance in neurons and astrocytes, which can initiate migraine attacks and lead to cortical spreading depression (CSD).

Serotonin Theory

Serotonin plays a direct role in the pathogenesis of migraine. Intermittent discharges from serotonergic neurons can provoke an initial excitation in the occipital cortex, which may either activate or suppress neuronal activity. According to many studies, serotonin is usually released from platelets at the onset of a migraine attack. Then, during the headache phase, its concentration drops, only to rise again in the interictal period. The most important serotonin receptors involved in migraine pathophysiology are 5-HT₁, 5-HT₂, and 5-HT₃, where 5-HT₁ is generally inhibitory, and 5-HT₂ is excitatory [10].

Genetic Theory

To date, the most studied genes associated with migraine—with or without aura—include MTDH, LRP1, PRDM16, MEF2D, ASTN2, and PHACTR1, all of which play a key role in neuronal and glutamatergic pathways. The TGFBR gene is responsible for vascular integrity and function, while the TRPM8 gene is directly involved in pain signal transmission. Genome-wide risk locus stratification studies have identified three variants specific to migraine with aura (MA): HMOX2, CACNA1A, and MPPED2, and two variants for migraine without aura (MwA): near SPINK2 and FECH. Additionally, nine more risk variants were found to be common across migraine types. The higher prevalence of migraine among females suggests hormonal or X-linked components in its pathogenesis. Furthermore, mitochondria are inherited exclusively from the mother, which implies a stronger maternal inheritance pattern. Twin and family studies have demonstrated a heritability rate of 49% for migraine attacks [11].

Trigeminovascular Theory.

At present, this is the most widespread and widely used concept. The core of this theory is that migraine develops as a result of depolarization of cortical neurons followed by a decrease in cerebral blood flow. The proposed mechanism involves dysfunction in ion channels of cortical neurons, which increases their excitability. This hyperexcitability allows various exogenous or endogenous factors to trigger episodes of regional neuronal hyperactivity, followed by cortical spreading depression (CSD). Typically, CSD begins in the occipital cortex and then spreads forward during the attack. Scientists believe that this mechanism is responsible for the aura and focal neurological symptoms observed in some patients. The precursors to CSD are transient ionic disturbances in neurons and neuroglia, which cause prolonged depolarization and suppression of electrical activity. CSD usually halts near the central sulcus, spreading ventrally and reaching the meningeal branches of the trigeminal nerve, thereby provoking cephalalgia [12].

Autonomic Nervous System

The autonomic nervous system (ANS) plays an extremely active role in the pathogenesis of migraine. In this condition, its dysfunction is manifested by a predominance of sympathetic-type disorders. In clinical practice, three trends are observed:

1. Migraine with aura (MA), compared to migraine without aura (MwA), is typically associated with more pronounced autonomic disturbances.
2. Sympathetic-type disorders are much more common than parasympathetic ones.
3. Sympathetic dysfunction is most prominent during the interictal period, with increasing sympathetic reactivity during the attack phase due to heightened adrenergic receptor sensitivity.

Despite the extensive study of these phenomena, it remains unclear whether the autonomic imbalance is a cause or consequence of migraine [4,13].

Immunological Theory

Previous studies have identified clear signs of immunodeficiency in patients with migraine and other primary headaches. These include changes in lymphocyte subpopulations, neutrophil function, decreased IgG levels, and cytokine imbalances. The most pronounced immune abnormalities were associated specifically with migraine and were linked to a more significant neurological burden compared to other headache types. Among the components of the immune system involved in migraine pathogenesis, cytokine status is of particular interest. Cytokines actively contribute to neurogenic inflammation, stimulate the synthesis of prostaglandins and leukotrienes, promote nitric oxide (NO) production by monocytes, activate platelets, and induce nociceptive neuron sensitization [14]. Cytokine concentrations in peripheral blood may serve as laboratory markers of immune deficiency or allergic pathology. Changes in cytokine levels in migraine patients—even in the absence of clinical symptoms—indicate a preclinical stage of immunopathology, in which cytokines may represent one of the pathogenetic links in headache development. Moreover, the progressive severity of immune disturbances correlates with disease duration, suggesting that immune mechanisms are involved in the chronicity of migraine [15].

Clinical Presentation in Children

In both children and adults, migraine is primarily associated with cephalalgia. In most pediatric cases, the headache begins in the morning. It is important to remember that morning headaches should not automatically be interpreted as a sign of increased intracranial pressure. In many cases, in addition to headaches, children may complain of periodic abdominal pain occurring without nausea, vomiting, cephalalgia, or visual changes.

The severity of cephalalgia tends to increase with physical activity and may be accompanied by nausea, vomiting, photophobia, and/or phonophobia. According to many authors, the periods of intense pain—especially in adolescents—are considered “lost time” in their lives. During the interictal period, some children exhibit dark circles under their eyes or a “migraine face”, which closely resembles the appearance of a child with allergies.

Age-Specific Clinical Features of Migraine in Children. Migraine manifestations in children vary with age.

- In infancy, the only sign may be episodic head shaking.
- As the child reaches preschool age, migraine often presents with a pale appearance, abdominal pain, vomiting, and a persistent desire to sleep. At this stage, pain is almost always accompanied by crying, increased irritability, body rocking, and a preference for darkness and solitude.

In children aged 5–10 years, migraine attacks often present with bifrontal, bitemporal, or retro-orbital localization, accompanied by nausea, abdominal spasms, vomiting, photophobia,

phonophobia, and a strong urge to sleep. These children often fall asleep after a period of extreme agitation, emotional lability, and crying — which frequently results in misdiagnoses of epileptic seizures.

In older children, migraine typically presents as unilateral pain in the temporal or temporo-orbital regions. However, it is important to note that in many cases, especially among pediatric and adolescent patients, the location and intensity of cephalalgia can vary, both during the same episode and between episodes. As children grow, both the intensity and duration of headache episodes tend to increase, eventually becoming similar in presentation to those observed in adults. Additionally, a notable number of cases involve spontaneous resolution of migraine attacks sometime after puberty [16].

Diagnosis

As previously mentioned, the diagnosis of migraine is based on the International Classification of Headache Disorders, 3rd Edition (ICHD-3), which includes specific diagnostic criteria for pediatric migraine [6,17].

The primary steps in diagnosing migraine include:

- Detailed medical history collection;
- Clinical and neurological examination;
- Mandatory exclusion of organic cerebral pathology.

A thorough description of the headache's clinical presentation, combined with neurological and physical assessment, helps physicians rule out so-called “red flags” — symptoms and signs that raise concern about secondary (symptomatic) headache [18].

Instrumental and Laboratory Diagnosis

Diagnostic efforts should be directed toward excluding other causes of cephalalgia and determining the etiology of the disorder. For instance, neuroimaging techniques are employed to exclude organic brain lesions, which may lead to secondary headache.

In such cases, the physician must thoroughly examine the structure of the brain and its meninges. To assess cerebral hemodynamics, MR angiography is recommended. In infants, MRI is typically replaced by neurosonography.

Special attention should be paid to proton magnetic resonance spectroscopy (¹H-MRS), a neuroimaging technique that enables the evaluation of major brain metabolites. This is critically important for understanding migraine pathogenesis and for early diagnosis, as MRS can detect metabolic changes in specific brain structures even before clinical symptoms appear.

In addition to neuroimaging, the following tests are commonly used:

- Electroencephalography (EEG);
- Transcranial Doppler sonography (TCD);
- Comprehensive immunological profiling (expanded immunogram) to assess immune system components.

Conclusion

Migraine is a fairly common condition in children and adolescents. As a rule, the pathology is characterized by periodic, unilateral (except in younger children), pulsating cephalalgia. It typically begins in childhood or early adulthood and tends to recur with decreasing frequency over the course of life. Cephalalgia in migraine is often accompanied by nausea, vomiting, photophobia, phonophobia, and visual disturbances. It is particularly important to note that migraine may initially present under the guise of various pediatric pathologies. In the pathogenetic mechanisms of migraine in children, in addition to the nervous system, a significant role is played by metabolic,

immune, and autonomic components. Based on this, early diagnosis, selection of appropriate therapy aimed at reducing the frequency of cephalalgia attacks and managing them effectively, as well as preventive treatment, will promote favorable outcomes of migraine in childhood.

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